

Ononin synergistically enhances the cytotoxic effect of doxorubicin in MDA-MB-231 triple-negative breast cancer cell line

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Abstract

Background: Triple-negative breast cancer (TNBC) represents approximately 15% of breast cancer cases worldwide. This subtype is characterized by aggressive behavior, poor prognosis, and a high recurrence rate. The lack of estrogen receptor alpha (ERα) renders hormonal therapies ineffective, leaving chemotherapy as the mainstay of treatment. However, chemotherapy often causes severe side effects. This study investigates the cytotoxic activity of ononin against TNBC *in vitro* and evaluates its potential to enhance the chemosensitivity of doxorubicin (DOX) in MDA-MB-231 cells.

Materials and methods: The effects of ononin and the ononin–DOX combination on cytotoxicity, migration, colony formation, and apoptosis were investigated.

Results: Ononin exhibited a cytotoxic effect against MDA-MB-231 cells, with an IC₅₀ of 50 μM, while DOX had an IC₅₀ of 1.8 μM. The CompuSyn-calculated combination index (CI) values indicated synergistic interactions, ranging from 0.23 to 0.08 at a constant DOX concentration of 1.8 μM. Analysis of the dose-reduction index (DRI) revealed 6.98-, 16.22-, and 66.86-fold reductions in the effective doses of DOX at ED₅₀, ED₇₅, and ED₉₅, respectively, when combined with a 10-fold concentration of ononin.

Combining 0.45 μM DOX with 6 μM ononin resulted in a significant decrease in colony formation compared with 0.45 μM DOX alone ($p < 0.0001$). Ononin also exhibited anti-migratory activity, and its combination with DOX further reduced cell migration compared with DOX alone after 72 hours ($p < 0.05$). However, ononin (25 μM) had no significant effect on caspase-3 gene expression.

Conclusion: This study is the first to demonstrate that ononin alone inhibits viability, migration, and colony formation in MDA-MB-231 cells and synergistically enhances the cytotoxic activity of DOX. These findings suggest that ononin may serve as a promising adjuvant agent to improve DOX efficacy in TNBC therapy.

Keywords

apoptosis, colony forming assay, cytotoxicity, MDA-MB-231, ononin, scratch assay

Introduction

Ononin (formononetin 7-O- β -D-glucopyranoside) is an isoflavone glycoside found in various plants of the Fabaceae family, including soybean (Osman and Fett 1983), liquorice (*Glycyrrhiza glabra* L.) (Benedec et al. 2012), chickpeas (*Cicer arietinum* L.) (Konar et al. 2014), sickle senna (*Cassia tora*) (Vijayalakshmi and Madhira 2014), and astragali radix (the roots of *Astragalus membranaceus* var. *mongholicus* a.k.a. *A. membranaceus*) (Chang et al. 2022; Cao et al. 2023). Several pharmacological activities of ononin have been reported, including anti-inflammatory (Chen et al. 2025), analgesic (Saqallah et al. 2025), antiadipogenic (Mladenova et al. 2022), nephroprotective (Dong et al. 2022), neuroprotective (Chen et al. 2021), antiangiogenic (Gong et al. 2021), and antioxidant activities (Li et al. 2025).

The anticancer properties of ononin have been demonstrated in several cancer cell lines. In osteosarcoma cells (MG-63 and U2OS), ononin downregulated the expression of matrix metalloproteinases (MMP-2 and MMP-9) and inhibited the epidermal growth factor receptor-extracellular signal-regulated kinase (EGFR-ERK1/2) signaling pathway (Gong et al. 2023). The administration of ononin successfully suppressed the growth of Hep-2 laryngeal cancer cells without affecting the survival of normal HuLa-PC laryngeal cells (Ye et al. 2022). Ononin suppressed the PI3K/Akt/mTOR pathway in the HCC827 and A549 non-small-cell lung cancer cell lines and reduced cell proliferation, invasiveness, and migration in the MCF-7 hormone-positive breast cancer cell line (Zuo 2020; Gong et al. 2022).

TNBC accounts for approximately 15% of breast cancer cases globally and is distinguished by its aggressive nature, poor prognosis, and high recurrence rate. Treatment options are limited to surgery, radiotherapy, and chemotherapy. Due to the lack of ER α expression, TNBC does not respond to hormonal therapy (Al-Kabariti and Abbas 2023).

Doxorubicin (DOX) serves as a cornerstone in chemotherapy protocols for various malignancies, including TNBC (Lafi et al. 2023). DOX intercalates between DNA base pairs, causing DNA damage that triggers a series of molecular signals, ultimately leading to apoptosis (Tacar et al. 2013). However, DOX therapy is limited by dose-dependent cardiotoxicity and the development of chemoresistance (Lafi et al. 2023). Consequently, devising new treatment strategies for TNBC with minimal side effects poses a significant challenge.

Combination chemotherapy provides a promising strategy to address these challenges by simultaneously targeting multiple cellular pathways, thereby producing additive or synergistic effects (Bisht et al. 2025). Unlike monother-

apy, which can non-selectively harm healthy proliferating cells and suppress bone marrow function, combination therapy allows for lower drug doses and potentially fewer side effects. This approach is increasingly emphasized for its ability to induce cytotoxicity in cancer cells while minimizing damage to normal cells. In particular, one drug in the combination may exert reduced toxicity on healthy cells, offering a protective effect against the cytotoxicity caused by the other agent (Vladu et al. 2022; Ibrahim et al. 2024). Additionally, combination therapy lowers the risk of resistance development by generating a more robust therapeutic response in a shorter period (Lafi et al. 2023).

In the search for more effective treatments, the potential of natural products as adjunct therapies has been explored (Ni et al. 2024). Therefore, this study aimed to evaluate the cytotoxic potential of ononin in MDA-MB-231 TNBC cells and assess its capacity to enhance the chemosensitivity of DOX. The study examined the individual and combined effects of ononin and DOX on cytotoxicity, migration, colony formation, and apoptosis.

Materials and methods

Cell culture

The MDA-MB-231 cell line was acquired from the American Type Culture Collection (ATCC, USA) and cultivated in DMEM high-glucose medium (Euroclone, Italy) supplemented with 10% fetal bovine serum, 1% penicillin-streptomycin, and 10 g/L L-glutamine, and incubated at 37 °C in a humidified 5% CO₂ incubator. Ononin (Sigma-Aldrich, USA; Cat. No. 486-62-4) was dissolved in dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO, ChemCruz, USA), ensuring that the final DMSO concentration did not exceed 0.1%.

Cell proliferation assay

MTT (3-(4,5-dimethylthiazol-2-yl)-2,5-diphenyl-tetrazolium bromide) (Promega, USA) assay was used to determine the effects of ononin, DOX, and their combinations on the MDA-MB-231 cell line. Cells were seeded into 96-well plates at a density of 10,000 cells per well in DMEM medium. Following a 24-hour incubation period, the cells were subjected to 72 h of exposure to either ononin, DOX, or a combination of both.

Combination index

The assessment of synergy was conducted by computing the combination index (CI) using Compusyn soft-

ware (version 1.0), downloaded freely from the official website (<https://compusyn.software.informer.com/1.0/>). A combination strategy using a constant-ratio model of 10 μM DOX to 100 μM ononin was utilized. Six twofold dilutions of this combination were tested. In addition, a non-constant-ratio design was employed, in which DOX was maintained at a fixed concentration of 1.8 μM , while ononin was tested at concentrations ranging from 50 μM to 0.78 μM . Cell viability was assessed after 72 h of treatment. CI values <1 , CI values $=1$, and CI values >1 indicate synergistic, additive, or antagonistic effects, respectively.

Colony formation assay

A clonogenic experiment was conducted to evaluate the ability of an individual cell to produce offspring and establish a colony, as previously described, with slight modifications. A total of 300 cells per milliliter were cultivated in DMEM containing 10% fetal bovine serum. After 24 hours, the cells were exposed to DOX or ononin at high (50 μM , half the IC_{50}) and low (25 μM , one-quarter of the IC_{50}) concentrations, either alone or in combination, for 72 h and incubated at 37 °C under 5% CO_2 . After 15 days, the cells were fixed by immersion in 4% paraformaldehyde for 1 hour, followed by washing with phosphate-buffered saline (PBS) and staining with 0.1% crystal violet. Subsequently, the colonies in each well were enumerated.

Scratch assay

The cell migration assay was performed as previously described (Al-Radaideh et al. 2025). Briefly, cells were seeded into 24-well plates at a density of 90×10^3 cells/mL. Subsequently, a sterile 100 μL plastic pipette tip was used to create parallel scratches, and the wells were rinsed with PBS to remove cellular debris. MDA-MB-231 cells were treated with either DOX or ononin, independently or in combination, at two distinct doses, with each condition performed in triplicate. The wound area was quantified using Motic software, version 2 (Motic China Group Co., Ltd.), at 24, 48, and 72 h. The wound area percentage was estimated using the previously described formula: wound area percent = (wound surface area at a specific time point in hours / wound surface area at zero time in hours) \times 100.

RNA extraction and quantitative real-time polymerase chain reaction (q-PCR)

The MDA-MB-231 cell line (10^6 cells) was cultured in DMEM medium. After 24 h, the culture medium was replaced with fresh medium. Subsequently, ononin (6 or 25 μM), DOX (1.8 or 0.45 μM), or a combination of ononin and DOX was added. Gene expression analysis was performed 72 h post-treatment. Total RNA was extracted using a Quick-RNA Miniprep Kit (Zymo, USA; Cat. No. R1055). One microgram of total cellular RNA, obtained from drug-treated cells, was used for cDNA synthesis. Re-

verse transcription was carried out using a ProtoScript kit (BioLabs, Cat. No. E6300S), according to the manufacturer's instructions, and a 2720 Thermal Cycler (Applied Biosystems). Real-time qPCR was performed using Entilink™ SYBR Green PCR Super Mix (ELK Biotechnology, Cat. No. EQ001) on the QuantStudio 5 system (Applied Biosystems by Thermo Fisher Scientific) under the following conditions: 95 °C for 30 seconds for one cycle, followed by 95 °C for 5 seconds, 62 °C (for *GAPDH* and *caspase-3*) for 30 seconds, and 72 °C for 30 seconds, repeated for 45 cycles. Melting curve analysis was conducted from 60 °C to 95 °C. The sense and antisense primers were obtained from Macrogen (South Korea). The sequence of the *caspase-3* primer was as reported in a previous study (Xiao et al. 2017; Table 1). The *GAPDH* gene was used as a housekeeping gene. Normalization of all expression data was achieved by dividing the target quantity by the quantity of *GAPDH* used as an internal reference for each sample.

Table 1. Sequences of primers.

Gene name or symbol	Primer sequence
<i>BAX</i>	Forward: 5'-TGGAGCTGCAGAGGATGATTG-3' Reverse: 5'-TGCCACTCGGAAAAAGACCT-3'
<i>BCL-2</i>	Forward: 5'-AAG CCG GCG ACG ACT TCT-3' Reverse: 5'-GGT GCC GGT TCA GGT ACT-3'
<i>Caspase-3</i>	Forward: 5'-AGCAAACCTCAGGGAAACATT-3' Reverse: 5'-CTCAGAAGCACACAACAAAACACT-3'
<i>GAPDH</i>	Forward: 5'-TGTGCCATCAATGACCCCTTC-3' Reverse: 5'-CTCCACGACGTACTCAGCGC-3'

Statistical analysis

The data were analyzed using one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA), followed by Tukey's post hoc test in GraphPad Prism, version 8 (GraphPad Software, San Diego, USA). Statistical significance was determined at $p < 0.05$, and the results are presented as mean \pm standard deviation (SD).

Results

Cytotoxic effect of ononin on the MDA-MB-231 cell line

As depicted in Fig. 1, ononin and DOX reduced MDA-MB-231 cell viability after 72 h, with IC_{50} values of 50 ± 5.00 μM for ononin and 1.8 ± 0.04 μM for DOX.

Ononin synergistically enhances the cytotoxic effect of DOX on the MDA-MB-231 cell line

The combination of DOX and ononin showed an enhanced reduction in cell viability in most combinations, with synergistic effects observed at both high and low doses of ononin at a constant DOX concentration of 1.8 μM . A flat sigmoidal ($m < 1$) curve was observed for

Figure 1. Cell viability of the MDA-MB-231 cell line tested by the MTT assay after 72 h of incubation with **A.** Ononin and **B.** DOX. Values are the average of triplicates and are presented as mean \pm SD.

DOX and ononin, with linear correlation coefficients (r) of approximately 0.93 for DOX and 0.95 for ononin (Fig. 2A). The CompuSyn-calculated CI values demonstrated synergistic interactions, with values ranging from 0.23 to 0.08. At the IC_{50} of both drugs, the CI was 0.23, while at half the IC_{50} of ononin, the CI was 0.14. In addition,

CI values of 0.09 and 0.07 were observed for combinations of ononin at $0.25 \times IC_{50}$ and $0.12 \times IC_{50}$, respectively, indicating that most ratios exerted synergistic effects against MDA-MB-231 cells. As shown in Fig. 2B, the CI-Fa plots further illustrated that CI values at different effect levels were <1 .

Figure 2. Effect curves generated from the CompuSyn calculation. **A.** Dose-effect curve for the non-constant ratio (IC_{50} of DOX and six dilutions of ononin). **B.** Dose-effect curve for the 1:10 DOX:ononin combination. **C.** Combination index plot among six combinations. **D.** Isobologram for the combination, indicating a synergistic effect ($CI < 1$).

When a constant ratio of both drugs was used, as shown in Fig. 2C, a flat sigmoidal ($m < 1$) curve was observed for DOX and ononin, with linear correlation coefficients (r) of approximately 0.93 for DOX and 0.95 for ononin, but less than 0.9 for the combination. Isobologram analysis showed that the data points for the combinations were below the lines of additivity at ED_{90} (Fig. 2D). Therefore, the combinations exhibited synergistic effects against MDA-MB-231 cells. To identify the most effective synergistic ratio, the CI for the DOX: ononin (1:10) treatment was < 1 at ED_{50} , ED_{70} , ED_{75} , ED_{80} , ED_{85} , ED_{90} , and ED_{95} (Suppl. material 1: table S1). Furthermore, analysis of the dose-reduction index (DRI) indicated 6.98-, 16.22-, and 66.86-fold

reductions in the effective doses of DOX at ED_{50} , ED_{75} , and ED_{95} , respectively, when combined with ononin.

Colony formation assay

Treatment with either DOX (1.8 or 0.45 μM) or ononin (25 or 6 μM) alone led to a significant reduction in colony formation compared with the control ($p = 0.0001$) (Figs 3, 4). The combination of 1.8 μM DOX with 25 μM ononin also resulted in a significant decrease in colony formation ($p = 0.0001$). Notably, the combination of 0.45 μM DOX with 6 μM ononin significantly reduced the number of colonies compared with 0.45 μM DOX alone ($p = 0.0001$).

Figure 3. Effect of ononin, DOX, and their combination on colony formation capability in MDA-MB-231 cells. **A.** Colony number after treatment with 6 μM ononin and 0.45 μM DOX compared with the control. **B.** Colony number after treatment with 25 μM ononin and 1.8 μM DOX, their combination, and the control after 15 days. Results are presented as mean \pm SD of three repeats. * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.0001$, **** $p < 0.0001$.

Figure 4. Colony formation capability of ononin, DOX, and their combination in MDA-MB-231 cells after 15 days.

Ononin enhanced the anti-migratory effect of DOX on the MDA-MB-231 cell line

The percentage of wound closure of the TNBC MDA-MB-231 cell line was reduced following treatment with ononin, DOX, and their combination (Fig. 5). Ononin (25

μM) resulted in wound area percentages of $97\% \pm 4.0$, $73\% \pm 5.1$, and $62\% \pm 10.6$ compared with $53\% \pm 9.5$, $19\% \pm 0.7$, and $0.8\% \pm 0.5$ for the control at 24 h, 48 h, and 72 h, respectively. Similarly, the low dose of ononin ($6 \mu\text{M}$) showed the same trend at 48 h and 72 h, with wound area percentages of $74\% \pm 5.7$ and $63\% \pm 3.4$ compared with

Figure 5. Effects of ononin, DOX, and their combined treatment on cell migration in the MDA-MB-231 cancer cell line as measured by the scratch assay. A–C. MDA-MB-231 cells treated with 1.8 μM DOX, 25 μM ononin, or their combination for 24 h, 48 h, and 72 h, respectively, with wound closure calculated relative to the initial scratch at day 0. D–F. MDA-MB-231 cells treated with 6 μM ononin, 0.45 μM DOX, or their combination for 24 h, 48 h, and 72 h, respectively. Data are presented as mean \pm SD. * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$, **** $p < 0.0001$.

the control values of $23\% \pm 2.9$ and $0.4\% \pm 0.1$, respectively, as shown in Fig. 5, Suppl. material 1: fig. S1.

The effect of the ononin–DOX combination treatment at different time intervals was also examined. The wound area percentage of MDA-MB-231 cells was $98.6\% \pm 9.87$ at the high-dose combination (25 μM ononin with 1.8 μM DOX) compared with the control ($1.0\% \pm 0.77$) and 1.8 μM DOX alone ($54\% \pm 3.7$) after 72 h. At low doses, ononin potentiated the anti-migratory effect of DOX, with a statistically significant difference compared with the control after 72 h, showing a wound area of $17\% \pm 2.42$ compared with the control ($0.4\% \pm 0.11$) (Fig. 5).

Effect of ononin, DOX, and their combination on the expression of apoptosis-related genes in the MDA-MB-231 cell line

A significant increase in caspase-3 expression was observed after DOX treatment (Fig. 6). Ononin (25 and 6 μM) increased caspase-3 expression; however, this upregulation was not statistically significant compared with the control. No synergistic apoptotic effect was exerted by the combination of ononin and DOX in the MDA-MB-231 cell line compared with DOX alone, as depicted in Fig. 6.

Figure 6. Effect of ononin, DOX, and their combination on Bax, Bcl-2, and caspase-3 gene expression in MDA-MB-231 cells. A, C, E. MDA-MB-231 cells treated with 1.8 μM DOX, 25 μM ononin, or their combination. B, D, F. MDA-MB-231 cells treated with 6 μM ononin, 0.45 μM DOX, or their combination.

DOX treatment significantly increased Bax expression and decreased Bcl-2 expression in MDA-MB-231 cells, indicating activation of a pro-apoptotic profile. Ononin alone caused only minor, non-significant changes in Bax and Bcl-2 levels. The combination of ononin with DOX did not further modulate Bax or Bcl-2 expression compared with DOX alone. These findings suggest that the synergistic cytotoxic effect of ononin and DOX is not mediated through additional Bax/Bcl-2-dependent apoptotic signaling.

Discussion

The primary objective of this study was to examine the cytotoxic effects of ononin on MDA-MB-231 cells and to assess whether ononin enhances the chemosensitivity of DOX in this TNBC cell line. If confirmed, this effect could allow for a reduction in the DOX dosage, potentially minimizing its toxicity to normal cells while preserving its anticancer activity. The results of the present study demonstrated a synergistic interaction between ononin and DOX in MDA-MB-231 cells. In addition, a previous *in vivo* study reported that ononin provided cardioprotective effects against DOX-induced myocardial damage in rats (Zhang et al. 2022).

The ability of ononin to inhibit colony formation suggests that it may exert its effects through cell cycle inhibition. Notably, it exhibited a synergistic effect when combined with DOX. The cell cycle-inhibitory properties of DOX have been well documented in previous studies (Sabzichi et al. 2019). However, this study is the first to report the impact of ononin on colony formation and migration and to suggest its potential to reduce the required dose of DOX.

In the current investigation, ononin exhibited anti-migratory effects against the human TNBC cell line. Similar results were observed in human osteosarcoma cells, where ononin significantly reduced invasion and migration in an MG-63 xenograft mouse model. The *in vivo* antitumorigenic and anti-migratory effects of ononin were attributed to its ability to suppress the protein expression of EGFR-ERK1/2 and MMP-2/9 (Gong et al. 2023). Similarly, ononin reduced invasive and migratory cell populations in MCF-7 cells through downregulation of MMP-9 expression (Zuo 2020). Furthermore, ononin depleted MMP expression in Hep-2 cells (Ye et al. 2022).

A prior investigation indicated that ononin inhibits the survival of MCF-7 breast cancer cells in a dose- and time-dependent manner. Upregulation of Bax expression and downregulation of Bcl-2 and PCNA expression were observed as consequences of this treatment (Zuo 2020). In addition, a 48-hour treatment with ononin significantly enhanced cellular apoptosis by increasing levels of apoptosis biomarkers, including cleaved caspase-3 and cleaved caspase-9, in A549 and HCC827 non-small-cell lung cancer cells (Gong et al. 2022). Ononin treatment (25 and 50 μ M) also significantly increased apoptosis in Hep-2 laryngeal carcinoma cells (Ye et al. 2022). In the present

study, ononin increased caspase-3 levels compared with the vehicle-treated control; however, this increase was not statistically significant.

The present study demonstrates that ononin exerts a cytotoxic effect against MDA-MB-231 triple-negative breast cancer cells and synergistically enhances the cytotoxicity of DOX, as evidenced by significant reductions in the effective doses (ED_{70} , ED_{75} , and ED_{90}) of DOX. Combination treatment also markedly decreased colony formation and cell migration compared with DOX alone, indicating enhanced antiproliferative and anti-migratory effects. However, the mechanistic basis underlying this synergistic effect remains unclear. Notably, treatment with ononin at 25 μ M did not alter caspase-3 expression, suggesting that the observed cytotoxicity may involve apoptosis-independent mechanisms or alternative apoptotic pathways that do not primarily rely on caspase-3 activation. Alternative mechanisms, including autophagy, necroptosis, cell cycle arrest, oxidative stress, or modulation of survival signaling pathways, may contribute to this effect and merit further investigation. The substantial reduction in effective DOX doses upon combination with ononin highlights the potential for achieving comparable cytotoxicity with lower drug concentrations, which could have implications for reducing systemic toxicities, such as cardiotoxicity, in future preclinical and translational studies. Overall, these data provide compelling evidence for the synergistic effects of ononin and DOX and underscore the potential of combination therapy as a strategy to enhance efficacy while potentially minimizing adverse effects.

Conclusion

This research provides the first evidence that ononin, when used independently, reduces MDA-MB-231 cell viability, migration, and colony formation. Moreover, it demonstrates a synergistic enhancement of the cytotoxic effect of DOX when combined with ononin. These findings provide preliminary evidence that ononin holds promise as an adjuvant therapy for the treatment of TNBC. However, further preclinical studies are warranted to more fully elucidate its therapeutic potential.

Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no informed consent was obtained from the humans, donors or donors' representatives participating in the study.

The authors declared that no experiments on animals were performed for the present study.

Use of commercially available immortalised human and animal cell lines: ATCC.

Use of AI

No use of AI was reported.

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Author contributions

M.A. and A.K. conceived and supervised the project. R.M. and A.K. performed the experiments. M.A.-Q. and Y.B. conducted

method validation and statistical analysis. M.A. wrote the manuscript. All authors read and approved the final article.

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Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text or Supplementary Information.

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Supplementary material 1

Supplementary table and figure

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Explanation note: **table S1.** Summary of CompuSyn-simulated CI and DRI values for the DOX and ononin combination in the MDA-MB-231 cell line at 70%, 75%, 80%, 85%, and 90% growth inhibition. **fig. S1.** Representative images of the scratch assay in MDA-MB-231 cells following treatment with ononin, DOX, or their combination for 72 h.

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